

Harumanis Luxe Bomb: Antioxidant Bath Bomb Enriched with Harumanis Mango Leaf Extract

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Abstract: *Harumanis mango (Mangifera indica var. Harumanis) leaves are rich in natural antioxidants and bioactive compounds, making them a promising ingredient in personal care innovations. This study presents the development of Harumanis Luxe Bomb, an eco-friendly bath bomb formulated using Harumanis mango leaf extract. The product aims to offer a natural alternative to synthetic-based bath products by utilizing plant-derived antioxidants known for their skin-soothing and rejuvenating properties. The leaves were extracted using ethanolic extraction, and the extract was incorporated into the bath bomb formulation. Preliminary antioxidant activity was confirmed via DPPH assay, indicating potential benefits for skin protection against oxidative stress. The bath bomb also demonstrated appealing effervescence, aroma, and skin feel during product testing. This innovation showcases the value-added potential of agricultural by-products and supports the development of sustainable, locally sourced wellness products.*

Keywords: *antioxidant; bath bomb; DPPH assay; Harumanis; mango.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the demand for natural and eco-friendly personal care products has increased significantly, driven by growing consumer awareness of sustainability and the potential health risks associated with synthetic ingredients (Peron, 2024). Bath bombs, a popular self-care item, are often enriched with essential oils and botanical extracts to enhance the bathing experience. However, many commercially available bath products still rely on artificial fragrances and colorants that may cause skin irritation or environmental harm (Peron, 2024).

Harumanis mango (*Mangifera indica* var. Harumanis) is a premium mango variety cultivated mainly in Perlis (located at northern part of Malaysia) prized for its aromatic fruit (Maharaj et al., 2022). While much attention has been given to the fruit itself, the leaves of the Harumanis mango tree are often discarded as agricultural waste despite being rich in polyphenols, flavonoids, and other bioactive compounds with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (Peron, 2024). These compounds make Harumanis mango leaves a promising natural ingredient for skincare and wellness applications.

This innovation explores the development of Harumanis Luxe Bomb, a bath bomb formulated using Harumanis mango leaf extract. The objective is to create a sustainable, skin-friendly product that not only repurposes agricultural by-products but also provides potential antioxidant benefits to users. This study outlines the extraction process, formulation, and functional evaluation of the bath bomb as a novel self-care product with added therapeutic value.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Sample Collection

Fresh Harumanis mango (*Mangifera indica* var. Harumanis) leaves were collected from UiTM Perlis, Malaysia. The leaves were thoroughly washed with distilled water, then dry in oven at 50°C for 3 days until fully dehydrated. Once dried, the leaves were ground into a fine powder using a laboratory blender and stored in an airtight container for extraction.

2.2 Extraction of Bioactive Compounds

The leaf powder was subjected to ethanolic extraction which 10 g of dried powder was macerated in 100 mL of distilled water for 24 hours, followed by filtration using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator and stored at 4°C until further use.

2.3 Antioxidant Activity Assay

The antioxidant activity of the Harumanis mango leaf extract was evaluated using the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay, and the absorbance was measured at 517 nm, and the percentage of radical scavenging activity was calculated (Sferrazzo et al., 2022). Results were compared against ascorbic acid, the antioxidant standard.

2.4 Formulation of Bath Bomb

The bath bomb was formulated using natural ingredients which include citric acid, sodium bicarbonate, cornstarch, epsom salt, Harumanis leaf extract, mango essential oil (for aroma), food coloring, and coconut oil (as a binder and skin moisturizer). The dry ingredients were mixed evenly before gradually adding the wet ingredients, including the mango leaf extract. The mixture was pressed into molds and allowed to dry at room temperature for 48 hours.

3. FINDINGS

The extraction process from Harumanis mango leaves produced a dark green extract with a mild herbal aroma. An antioxidant assay was conducted to evaluate the potential of Harumanis mango leaf extract in the bath bomb formulation. The assay indicated the presence of antioxidant activity, suggesting that the extract contains bioactive compounds capable of contributing to skin protection and overall product enhancement (Sferrazzo et al., 2022). The observed activity supports the use of Harumanis leaves as a functional natural ingredient in personal care formulations.

The formulated bath bomb containing Harumanis mango leaf extract exhibited mild mango-fruity scent due to the inclusion of mango essential oil complemented the herbal scent of the leaf extract, resulting in a refreshing and soothing aroma. The coconut oil provided additional moisturizing benefits. The bath bombs maintained good structural integrity during storage at room temperature for

over a week, showing no signs of cracking or crumbling. The color remained stable, and the product retained its aromatic profile throughout the observation period.

4. DISCUSSION

The development of Harumanis Luxe Bomb demonstrates the potential of Harumanis mango (*Mangifera indica* var. Harumanis) leaves as a value-added ingredient in personal care products (Hoang et al., 2021). Although the fruit is well-known for its premium quality, the leaves are often underutilized or discarded (Peron et al., 2024). This study highlights their potential use, particularly due to their antioxidant properties. The antioxidant capacity of the extract supports its application in skincare, where protection against oxidative stress and environmental damage is beneficial. Furthermore, the use of locally sourced botanical waste (mango leaves) also aligns with the principles of sustainability and circular economy, which are increasingly emphasized in product development and research (Peron, 2024).

The successful incorporation of the leaf extract into a bath bomb formulation indicates good compatibility with common ingredients such as baking soda, citric acid, and essential oils. The final product maintained structural integrity and showed good effervescence, two key consumer expectations for bath bombs (Peron, 2024). The mango-fruity aroma created a pleasant sensory experience, while the coconut oil addition contributed to a moisturized skin feel post-application (Peron, 2024). These features make the product not only functional but also appealing to eco-conscious consumers.

Overall, this innovation bridges the gap between agriculture and wellness industries, demonstrating how traditional plants and agro-waste can be transformed into high-value self-care products. Future studies may explore extended shelf-life testing, in-depth phytochemical analysis, and dermatological evaluations to strengthen the scientific foundation and commercial viability of the product.

5. CONCLUSION

This study was carried out to develop a bath bomb using Harumanis leaves as a natural ingredient. The results showed that Harumanis leaf extract has successfully incorporated into bath bomb formulations, with potential skin benefits. This project highlights the potential of local agricultural waste like Harumanis leaves can be innovatively used in personal care products. Further research can explore improvements in formulation stability and shelf life.

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References

- Hoang, H. T., Moon, J., & Lee, Y. (2021). Natural Antioxidants from Plant Extracts in Skincare Cosmetics: Recent Applications, Challenges and Perspectives. *Cosmetics*, 8(4), 106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cosmetics8040106>
- Maharaj, A., Naidoo, Y., Dewir, Y. H., & Rihan, H. (2022). Phytochemical Screening, and Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activities of *Mangifera indica* L. Leaves. *Horticulturae*, 8(10), 909. <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae8100909>
- Peron, R. V., Bakar, A. R. A., Zainuddin, M. A. M., Yee, A. Q., Daud, N. M. A. N., Rahman, A. M. A., & Khairuddin, N. H. (2024). Insights into the pharmacognostic elucidation of Harumanis mango (*Mangifera indica* Linn.) leaves extracts as therapeutic agent. *Journal of Advanced Research in Micro and Nano Engineering*, 17(1), 28-41.
- Sapin, A. B., Alaon, M. K. N., Tambalo, F. M. Z., Perez, R. H., & Gaylon, A. (2021). Evaluation of the bioactivities of natural phenolics from mango (*Mangifera indica* Linn) leaves for cosmetic industry applications. *Philipp. J. Sci*, 150, 397-406.
- Sferrazzo, G., Palmeri, R., Restuccia, C., Parafati, L., Siracusa, L., Spampinato, M., Carota, G., Distefano, A., Di Rosa, M., Tomasello, B., Costantino, A., Gulisano, M., Volti, G. L., & Barbagallo, I. (2022). *Mangifera indica* L. Leaves as a Potential Food Source of Phenolic Compounds with Biological Activity. *Antioxidants*, 11(7), 1313. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11071313>